

Tracing Textual Genesis Through Parts-of-Speech-Tagging of Selected Poems by Friederike Mayröcker

Möglichkeiten und Methoden zur Untersuchung von Textgenese
mithilfe quantitativer Textanalyse am Beispiel von Parts-of-Speech-Tagging
ausgewählter Gedichte von Friederike Mayröcker

supervisor: Ass.-Prof. Mag. Mag. Dr. Andreas Baumann

PRESENTATION: MASTER THESIS - JOHANNA UNTERHOLZNER
04.12.2025: RE-LATE - RE-USE - RE-VISE

Research Questions

- What are the steps and methods that are needed to help model the text genesis with several text witnesses and revision stages and prepare them for a quantitative analysis?
- To what extent can quantitative text analysis focused on parts of speech provide insights into possible editing tendencies in the case study?

Research Question I

What are the steps and methods that are needed to help model the text genesis with several text witnesses and revision stages and prepare them for a quantitative analysis?

Corpus

Alp-Traum[°]

(12.01.1981; W129/480), 4 witnesses

Newtonringe[°]

(03.03.1981; W129/480), 8 witnesses

*Rosenfragment**

(02./03.10.1981; W127/471), 5 witnesses

*Wassersachen, nach Mimmo Paladino**

(11.10.1981; W127/471 & W129/479), 5 witnesses

*vielleicht weil das Auge zuerst bricht**

(23./25.10.1981; W127/471), 7 witnesses

[°]Mayröcker, Friederike (1982): Gute Nacht, guten Morgen. Gedichte 1978-1981. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp Verlag

*Mayröcker, Friederike (1986): Winterglück. Gedichte 1981-1985. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp Verlag

Transcription

- witnesses & published version
- standardization (spelling, Eszett/sz, stenography, ...)

POS-Tagging

- python-library SpaCy
- Transformer model: de_dep_news_trf
- Suffixes

Modeling

XML/TEI

handwritten revisions:

- additions <add>
- deletions
- more complex revisions <choice> <orig> <reg>

```
<choice><orig> riesigen_/ADJ</orig> <reg change="#blue_pen"> riesige_/ADJ</reg></choice>  
<add change="#blue_pen"> Dolche_/NOUN</add>  
<del change="#blue_pen"> Eiszapfen_/NOUN</del>
```

(Alp-Traum, witness 1)

attribut @change

attribut value = pen color

token-level: Prinzip Edition*

*Brüning, Gerrit (2022): Modellierung von Textgeschichte. Bedingungen digitaler Analyse und Schlussfolgerungen für die Editorik. In: Fotis Jannidis (Hg.): Digitale Literaturwissenschaft. DFG-Symposion 2017. Stuttgart: J.B. Metzler Verlag, S. 307–338.

Extraction

- pen color ~ text stage
- XPath
- Python-Library lxml

Research Question II

To what extent can a quantitative text analysis focused on parts of speech provide insights into possible editing tendencies in the case study?

Mayröcker's style of writing

- existing analyses by Combrink, Kastberger and Mayröcker herself
- operationalizing their observations
- simplified:
 - elaborations/cuts => text length / total number of tokens
 - revisions => occurrence of <add>, , ...
 - repetitions/alliterations => search for sequences
 - ellipsis => absence of certain POS
 - irregularities regarding POS distribution
 - punctuation => minor tendencies 3:2

Combrink, Thomas (2016): Friederike Mayröcker. In: Hermann Korte (Hg.): Kindler Kompakt Österreichische Literatur der Gegenwart. Stuttgart: J.B. Metzler, S. 61–67.

Kastberger, Klaus (2000): Reinschrift des Lebens. Friederike Mayröckers 'Reise durch die Nacht'. Edition und Analyse. Wien u.a.: Böhlau Verlag.

Mayröcker, Friederike (1983): MAIL ART. In: Friederike Mayröcker: Magische Blätter. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp Verlag, S. 9–35.

Results

manual revisions
• varied intensity

pen colors
& revision type

Abbildung 34: Absolute Häufigkeitsverteilung aller Attributwerte (Stiftfarben) für die Textzeugen des Gedichts *VWDAZB*.

Results

tokens involved in revisions

- more in <add> & <reg>

POS in revisions

- nouns (1/4 of all tokens)
- punctuation: heavily deleted
- verbs appear infrequently

Abbildung 21: Absolute Häufigkeitsverteilung der Parts of Speech in allen Eingriffs-Tags des Gedichts *NWTRG*.

Results

total number of tokens

- increase: revision stages
- decrease: new transcription
> published version

Abbildung 29: Absolute Häufigkeitsverteilung der Parts of Speech im Gedicht *WSNMP* über alle Textzeugen und deren Revisionsstufen hinweg bis zur publizierten Fassung.

Results

frequency distributions of POS

- revisions often no effect on POS or contradictory
- general increase: nouns

Revisions' impact on POS

- semantic level: „Feld“ > „Acker“ > „Stoppelfeld“
(*Wassersachen, nach Mimmo Paladino, witness 3ff*)
- word stem preserved: „erkennen“ > „erkennbar“
(*Rosenfragment, witness 1*)

Results

many occurring sequences

- determiner – adjective – noun: „die jungen Fremden“
(*Alptraum*)
- preposition – determiner – noun: „aus der Maschine“
(*vielleicht weil das Auge zuerst bricht*)
- determiner & nouns: „den Mond, das Land“
mostly enumerations, not genitive constructions
(*ebd.*)

alliterations

- „Farbstich, Fremdflocke “
(*Rosenfragment, witness*)
- newly added nouns

Summary

focus on POS suggest small changes in genesis

Corpus is expandable => clearer results

POS: only the starting point => extendable with further aspects (lemmatization, ...)

proven assumptions concerning Mayröcker's writing style

Unterholzner, Johanna: *Möglichkeiten und Methoden zur Untersuchung von Textgenese mithilfe quantitativer Textanalyse am Beispiel von Parts-of-Speech-Tagging ausgewählter Gedichte von Friederike Mayröcker*. Masterarbeit 2024, <https://theses.univie.ac.at/detail/73664>.